

CARING FOR CANCER PATIENTS AND THEIR FAMILIES: THE LIVED EXPERIENCES OF NURSING STUDENTS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13291979>

ABSTRACT

This qualitative study examines the experiences of nursing students providing care for cancer patients and their families. The study uses thematic analysis to identify themes and patterns in the experiences of sixteen students through in-depth interviews. The results reveal a complex environment with strong emotional bonds, career advancement, and the importance of support networks. Nursing students reported various emotions, including nervous anticipation, empathy, and resilience, as they navigated the complexities of cancer care. Challenges such as lack of professional experience and perceived limitations were mitigated by guidance and support from mentors and peers. The study underscores the importance of comprehensive education and support systems to prepare nursing students for the emotional and practical demands of oncology nursing.

Keywords: *Cancer care, nursing students, lived experiences, qualitative research, thematic analysis, emotional challenges, support systems.*

INTRODUCTION

Nursing education is a complex process that combines classroom learning with practical clinical experiences. Understanding nursing students' perceptions of these experiences is crucial for assessing the effectiveness of clinical education in preparing future nurses. Clinical experiences significantly influence students' confidence, competence, and professional identity. A study focusing on nursing students' experiences caring for cancer

patients and their families is essential for nursing education practices. Duchscher (2008). By identifying potential gaps in education and training, curricula can be tailored to better prepare students for complex and critically ill patients.

The stress, grief, and moral dilemmas they encounter in these situations can be overwhelming (Hoover et al., 2010). The emotional and psychological toll of caring for cancer patients and their families can be overwhelming, leading to the development of support mechanisms and interventions that enhance students' resilience, coping strategies, and emotional well-being. The relationships between nursing students, cancer patients, and their families are central to holistic, patient-centered care, which can improve communication and patient-family interaction, leading to enhanced patient outcomes and satisfaction.

Understanding these dynamics can contribute to improved communication and patient-family interaction, leading to enhanced patient outcomes and satisfaction (Babore et al., 2018).

In conclusion, a study examining the lived experiences of nursing students in caring for cancer patients and their families can improve nursing education, enhance student support systems, and ultimately benefit patient care quality. By addressing the emotional, psychological, and educational aspects of these experiences, this research can contribute to a more compassionate and competent nursing workforce and improved patient outcomes.

The research study utilizes Albert Bandura's Social Cognitive Theory, George Engel's Biopsychosocial Model, and Jean Watson's Theory of Human Caring to understand the complex nature of caring for cancer patients and their families. Bandura's theory emphasizes the importance of modeling, imitation, and observational learning in developing new behaviors and abilities, making it relevant to nursing students. Engel's biopsychosocial model considers social, psychological, and biological aspects of cancer treatment, emphasizing the connections between health and well-being. Watson's Theory of Human Caring emphasizes the importance of caring as a universal human experience, transcending cultural barriers, and provides guidance for researchers studying the complex interactions between emotions, relationships, and the human spirit in healthcare settings.

Research Questions

This qualitative study investigates the challenges faced by student nurses in providing comprehensive care for cancer patients and their families, highlighting the potential for stress, burnout, and discontent, as a result of their limited knowledge and abilities.

1. What are the experiences of the nursing students during oncology placement in the hospital?
2. What are the triumphs and challenges of student nurses when taking care of a cancer patient?

3.What did the nursing students feel during the oncology placement in the hospital?

Assumptions

Nursing students' experiences in caring for cancer patients and their families are significantly shaped by the emotional and psychological challenges they encounter, as well as the support and guidance they receive from mentors and the healthcare team.

METHODOLOGY

This chapter details the research design, setting, instruments, respondents, data procedure, and ethical considerations for the study "Caring for cancer patients and their families: The lived experiences of nursing students." The study aims to improve coping strategies for future nursing students.

The study analyzed the experiences of third-year nursing students at the University of San Carlos in caring for cancer patients during their oncology placement. Using a descriptive phenomenological research design, the researchers conducted one-on-one interviews with respondents to understand the challenges and aspects of their care. The study included male and female third-year nursing students who had experienced duty rotations at the Cebu Cancer Institute Hospital. The participants were chosen based on their mental health and experience in caring for sick patients. The study excluded individuals who were not enrolled in the nursing department, Level 3 students, had not had a duty rotation, or had a cognitive-affecting condition. The research aimed to identify common themes and patterns in the experiences of nursing students caring for cancer patients.

The study utilized the interview guide method, a structured qualitative research method that uses open-ended questions to facilitate in-depth conversations between researchers and participants. This method aims to gather nuanced insights into an individual's experiences, perspectives, or opinions on a specific topic, ensuring consistency across interviews and flexibility to explore emergent themes.

The researchers certified interview questions with an oncology clinical nurse, aiming to elicit thoughtful answers about the practical, psychological, and emotional aspects of providing treatment in cancer settings. The questions aimed to elicit reflections from participants about their experiences, obstacles, and tactics for empathetic care, promoting open discourse and discussing their lived experiences.

- 1.Could you tell us how you feel about your oncology placement in the hospital?
 - 1.1 How do you feel when you are working with cancer patients?
 - 1.2 How many hours are you exposed in your oncology placement?
 - 1.3 Do you feel worried, stressed, depressed, or alright during your oncology placement?

2. What are the problems and challenges encountered during your oncology placement?
 - 2.1 Can you describe these difficulties?
 - 2.2 Why do you think you are having these difficulties?
3. How did you overcome the problems you had when working with cancer patients?
 - 3.1 What do you do to maintain a sense of emotional and mental control during your oncology placement?
 - 3.2 What are your suggestions for minimizing the impact of facing the challenges of taking care of a cancer patient?

The University approved and reviewed and approved the research paper prior to the study's implementation. The researchers conducted face-to-face interviews with third year nursing students, adhering to the Data Privacy Act of 2012, which requires the anonymization of respondent names and the separation of personally identifiable information from research results. This act protects the privacy rights and dignity of participants in sensitive studies involving healthcare experiences.

The study adhered to strict confidentiality guidelines, respecting the privacy rights of participants, and fostering confidence between participants and researchers. The data was discarded after usage, and participants provided 15 minutes to answer questions without compensation. Data analysis was handled by researchers using industry-standard encryption algorithms to secure sensitive data. The encrypted files were stored on password-protected devices, accessible only to authorized researchers and advisers. Regular audits and monitoring procedures were implemented to trace access and identify illegal attempts to compromise the system. Hard copies of confidential documents were retained in an expanded plastic envelope, ensuring the integrity and confidentiality of the data for the duration of the study.

The study employed Braun and Clarke's thematic analysis, which involves familiarizing oneself with the data through transcription, reading, and re-reading. Initial codes are generated by identifying relevant segments, and codes are collated into potential themes. Data is gathered for each theme, including respondent verbatim and related studies. Themes are named and accurately represent the data, and the final output is related to the research questions and related literature.

The study focuses on the reliability and quality of qualitative research, as proposed by Lincoln and Guba in their 1985 book "Naturalistic Inquiry." The researchers used the phenomenological theory to ensure a systematic and well-structured approach to understanding nursing students' experiences. They obtained ethical approvals, confidentiality, and informed consent from participants before conducting the study. The findings were shared with participants to ensure accurate representation.

Transferability was achieved through direct participant quotes and examples from the interview, with member checking as a validation strategy. The study's transferability is

discussed in the scope and limitations, and practical recommendations are provided based on the findings.

Dependability was achieved through a descriptive phenomenological research design and the interview method, which aligns with the research questions. Regular consultation sessions with knowledgeable instructors were conducted to identify potential biases or gaps. Consistency in the data collection process was observed to reduce variability. Findings were presented to participants for feedback and alignment with their lived experiences.

Confirmability was achieved through open-ended questions for interviews, participant statements, and transparent documentation of modifications and progress through a Gantt chart. These elements of methodological rigor are essential for assessing the rigor and quality of qualitative research.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Theme 1. Professional Inexperience

Albert Bandura's social cognitive theory emphasizes the importance of guided learning and practical experience in clinical placements. These placements allow students to apply theoretical knowledge in real-life situations, witness best practices, and receive feedback. However, students often lack knowledge and experience in cancer care, leading to difficulties in providing quality care. A 2018 study by Kapucu & Bulut found students feeling inadequate and powerless in providing quality care and struggling to adjust to the fast-paced environment and workload due to the disproportionate ratio of patients to nurses.

Skill Deficit. Many students felt that their clinical skills were insufficient for the demands of cancer care.

Respondent 1: "There are many unfamiliar drugs. Also, the work there was very fast that we didn't know what to do in the facility" (2:59-3:06)

Respondent 13: "Due to the greater ratio of patients, we, the student nurses along with the nurses, had to work double time just to cater to everyone's treatment and care." (2:02-2:12)

Lack of Knowledge. There is insufficient knowledge and information prior to the rotation.

Respondent 4: "In a general sense, it's a new ward, so thereby it's a new topic and thereby it's a whole lot of new things" (1:08 - 1:17)

Respondent 12: "Maybe because you are new to the place, you have recently been put in the area, in that rotation. It was your 1st time to encounter... that situation." (3:50 - 4:15)

Theme 2. Nervous Anticipation

Student nurses often experience nervous anticipation before starting clinical rotations in oncology. This anxiety is a major subject, combining anxiety, doubt, and excitement. A study from Turkey by Kapucu & Bulut in 2018 found that students experienced extreme anxiety during their first clinical experience in an oncology service. Social cognitive theory suggests modelling and observational learning can help reduce anxiety related to anticipation. Students can develop coping mechanisms by observing experienced nurses handle difficult situations. The biopsychosocial model explains that physiologic stress responses, psychological fear, and social pressures contribute to anxiety. Resolving these issues can help reduce anxiety.

Fear of the Unknown. The anticipation of encountering new and challenging situations was a common source of nervousness.

Respondent 1: "At first, I was nervous because I didn't have any idea in taking care of these types of patients." (1:45 - 1:50)

Respondent 5: "It was a mix of fear and, of course, excitement for the exposure." (0:05 - 0:10)

Anxiety. Respondents expressed uncertainty about their ability to handle the emotional demands of caring for cancer patients.

Respondent 6: "From when I first heard that we were going to have our oncology replacement during our hospital, for our clinical duties, I think I was a bit anxious in finding out that we were going to be handling patients of all kinds of prognosis." (1:46 - 2:05)

Respondent 8: "So, at first I was anxious because it's my first time being assigned there and... yeah mostly anxious" (0:08 - 0:25)

Theme 3. Reflective Engagement

Reflective engagement in nursing involves examining events through biology, psychology, and society, promoting lifelong learning and professional development. This approach helps nursing students identify strengths and areas for growth. Examining emotional experiences, such as empathy and anxiety, can improve preclinical training and patient care. (Kapucu, 2017) Oncology placements significantly impact nursing students' emotional well-being and professional growth, highlighting the importance of reflective engagement.

Self-Reflection. Regular self-reflection helped students understand their experiences and improve their practice.

Respondent 4: "I am the nurse. I am a student nurse and, of course, I am trying to learn, but at the same time, I'm still giving you my quality care." (5:07 - 5:16)

Respondent 16: "In having these difficulties, keep a clear mind, reflect, or rationalize your interventions, and most importantly, understand them." (3:37 - 4:00)

Professional Growth. Reflection contributed to their professional development and preparedness for future challenges.

Respondent 4: “If you want to foresee, you want to understand what you want to foresee, of course, you need to learn, and learning takes a long process. And as we know, everyone grows at different paces, and everyone learns at different paces. Sometimes, students learn for two weeks, sometimes a student can learn it in a day, so it’s a matter of creating a more inclusive period for all students to learn the topic, so much so that it’s sufficient enough for them to understand, thereby anticipate and foresee on how they would administer their quality nursing care.” (11:34 - 12:15)

Respondent 5: “The difficulties were a challenge I was really willing to pick up on.” (2:40 - 2:45)

Theme 4. Guidance and Support

Peers who provide support and guidance are crucial in nursing education, as they offer opportunities for modelling, constructive conduct, and self-efficacy development. Mentors can also aid in resilience and confidence building. A supportive atmosphere with mentorship, psychological stress management skills, and sufficient therapeutic resources is essential. The study by Moghimian et al’s (2018) highlights that collaboration with peers allows nursing students to share experiences, exchange knowledge, and provide mutual encouragement, fostering a supportive learning environment. Providing guidance and support improves confidence, nursing knowledge, skills, psychosocial well-being, self-development, and insights needed for end-of-life care. (Kent et al., 2012).

Mentorship. The presence of supportive instructors and staff helped students navigate their clinical placements.

Respondent 1: “Maybe with the help of the CCI nurses and also our CI, I think we managed working with cancer patients” (3:29 - 3:37)

Respondent 3: “What I did, was to ask for help, ask for guidance, especially to the nurses in the facilities, to be able for them to help me and my challenges.” (4:57 - 5:10)

Peer Support. Sharing experiences and challenges with fellow students provided a sense of solidarity.

Respondent 9: “I tried to talk to my other groupmates, or other student nurses, about my feelings, so that my feelings will not be bottled up” (4:47 - 4:55)

Respondent 14: “By helping each other as a team like sharing learnings, cooperating with each other when there are necessary times to be handled, was also the reason that brought us to a meaningful exposure” (2:41 - 2:55)

Theme 5. Perceived Limitations

The biopsychosocial model suggests that nursing students may feel limited in their capacity to provide care due to deficiencies in three domains: psychological unpreparedness, lack of biological information, and social difficulties. In an oncology placement, students face limitations in providing quality care to cancer patients due to knowledge gaps and skills gaps. (Sanford et.al., 2011. A 2012 study from Komprood found that limited information given to students before the rotation affected their service,

and the curricula's narrow focus on cancer nursing further limited their exposure and knowledge.

Knowledge Gaps. Students expressed concerns about their lack of comprehensive medical knowledge.

Respondent 2: "For me, it was due to not enough information or I wasn't able to retain the information or knowledge that I get through books. I wasn't able to apply them properly." (4:45 - 5:08).

Respondent 6: "Really, because we're student nurses where there are limitations of what we can, of what we can do, of what we can do as student nurses. We can't insert IVs, we can't do this, we can't do that." (6:45 - 7:00)

Emotional Boundaries. Many students struggled to maintain emotional boundaries, feeling deeply affected by their patients' conditions.

Respondent 6: "It's really hard to see them being in that state knowing that they could have had their whole lives ahead of them, but instead you know like that." (4:46 - 4:55)

Respondent 10: "So apart from that the challenges would be..... separating your, your emotions for the best intervention available." (5:00 - 5:15)

Theme 6. Resilience

Resilience in nursing students can be developed through observing and imitating others' actions, developing psychological coping mechanisms, enhancing confidence through practical experience, and receiving social support from peers and mentors. The biopsychosocial model emphasizes resilience as a multifaceted concept, demonstrating it through staying focused, seeking support from peers and mentors, and finding meaning in their work despite personal challenges. This helps nursing students deliver quality care to the best of their capabilities. (Moghimian et al, 2019).

Adaptability. Students learned to adapt quickly to the challenging conditions.

Respondent 9: "I overcame the problems I had in working with cancer patient by adapting to the environment" (3:47 - 3:54).

Respondent 14: "However, a few days have passed, and we were able to adapt to our RLE exposure." (1:15 - 1:21)

Emotional Strength. Developing emotional strength was essential for coping with the stressors of the role.

Respondent 4: "During that time, it's a matter of, again, willpower. Understanding that, okay, they [the patients] are pitiful, but at the same time, you have the responsibility over them, so you have to power through again." (9:00 - 9:14).

Respondent 7: "I guess the biggest way I overcame those challenges was through, as cheesy as it may sound, determination and remembering your purpose" (8:06 - 8:18)

Conclusions

The study reveals the emotional and practical challenges faced by third-year nursing students during their oncology placement at the University of San Carlos. The students experienced anxiety and excitement, reflecting their response to a new environment. Initially, they felt inadequacy and perceived limitations, but overcame these through strategic support systems and reflective practices. The students experienced a range of emotions, from fear and stress to a growing sense of confidence and accomplishment. The study emphasizes the importance of structured support and mentorship in helping nursing students manage the complexities of cancer care, enhancing their ability to provide compassionate care while maintaining their psychological well-being. The students' resilience, support, and reflective practices contributed to a positive overall outcome, with a sense of accomplishment and professional growth. The overall experience was not predominantly negative, highlighting the importance of structured support and mentorship in nursing education.

Recommendations

The nursing curriculum should include more comprehensive oncology care modules to equip students with the necessary knowledge and skills to provide quality treatment to cancer patients and their families. Resources should be allocated for training sessions focusing on psychological support, palliative care, and empathic communication. Mentorship programs should also be established.

Nursing instructors should employ experiential learning techniques like role-plays, simulations, and case studies to enhance students' understanding of the psychosocial aspects of cancer treatment. They should encourage empathy and self-awareness by encouraging reflection on their experiences. Clinical instructors should provide comprehensive orientations to students about their roles and responsibilities during their oncology placement.

Nursing students can enhance their understanding of cancer patients' psychological and emotional needs through programs that emphasize empathy and self-care. They can avoid burnout and compassion fatigue by scheduling regular debriefing meetings with mentors or peers and receiving group or individual feedback from clinical instructors to develop future coping strategies.

Cancer patients and their families can effectively communicate their choices, concerns, and needs to healthcare providers. They can also utilize resources from community organizations or medical facilities like support groups and counselling programs. Patients can actively participate in their care by asking questions, researching treatments, and sharing their beliefs and choices.

Researchers are exploring the impact of cultural, socioeconomic, and regional characteristics on nursing students' experiences caring for cancer patients and their families. They aim to evaluate the impact of nursing education and training on the

standard of care, enhancing the nursing curriculum and clinical practice. They also explore new approaches to address the psychological needs of cancer patients and their families.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Minimizing the risk of harm

The study aims to minimize the risk of harm by providing participants with a low level of risk during the interview process. Participants may reveal personal information, making them feel uncomfortable, but the researchers expect a low level of risk. They can withdraw their participation at any time without penalty or loss of benefits. A debriefing session is provided to ensure participants are well and safe after the interview.

The study involved an interview intervention, participant selection, and data preservation. Participants were informed about the purpose, procedure, benefits, and duration of the interview. Researchers ensured data safety and confidentiality by keeping each participant's unique number assigned and data linked to it. Participants were not given information outside the research team, and transcripts and data were destroyed after use. Participants were informed they could decline participation or withdraw at any time, and no adverse consequences would be expected if they refused or withdrawn. Researchers obtained separate consent for participation and interview recording, and participants could contact the researchers with any questions about the research or their rights. The study aimed to maintain anonymity and confidentiality.

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